

INFLUENCE OF SIMULATED SERVICE CONDITIONS ON THE RELIABILITY OF POLYARAMID COMPOSITE TENSION MEMBERS

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ABSTRACT

The outstanding specific tensile strength properties of unidirectional polyaramid fibre ropes and composite tendons have allowed these materials to be considered for highly demanding tethering applications, e.g. as offshore platform anchor systems. The requirement for high levels of reliability, longevity and safety in service are paramount, yet the physical size and geometry of such components is such that proof testing or NDE in the field is difficult. This leads to the necessary use of high design factors, less than optimum structural efficiency, and high costs.

The work here presents a model for estimating the expected tensile strength of assemblies of very long pultruded polyaramid tension members, under the effect of simulated marine exposure. The results indicate that the effect of absorbed water is small compared to the effects of realistic material variability and component size. It is predicted that the expected safe working load of large tendons in service (1000m long by 100kN breaking load) can be as little as 1/10 of the mean strengths measured in tests on conventional laboratory testpieces.

KEYWORDS: Aramid; Strength; Reliability; Environmental effect; Failure.

1. INTRODUCTION

The outstanding specific strengths available from polyaramid ropes and composite tendons has led these materials to be used as high performance tension members in a number of applications, e.g. offshore moorings, civil structures and guyed masts (1). It has now been well established that in comparison to steel ropes, polyaramid ropes can offer upto five times the load carrying capacity for the same weight of steel in air, and upto fifteen times that of steel under water (2); with resin impregnated composite tendons of the same

fibre showing even larger savings in weight. These properties, coupled with good environmental and fatigue performance mean that the types of application most likely to benefit from the use of polyaramid ropes and tendons are those where very long lengths are required to carry high loads in weight sensitive structure under exposed conditions. Floating oil-platform anchors are a typical example (3). This application is safety critical, yet there are no accepted methods available for NDE of the components in service, nor is it possible to proof test in the lab or field. In addition, the environments that such components work in can be extreme, e.g. submerged in deep seawater, exposed to hydrocarbons, physical handling damage, combined with complex fluctuating loads.

The demand for reliable and safe performance without the weight and cost penalties of over-design, and lack of proof testing and inspection place a critical emphasis on predictive design methods and data employed.

The present paper presents a framework for the prediction of the expected failure probabilities under static loads of representative full size polyaramid composite tendons (e.g. 1000m long by 100 kN breaking load) in the wet condition. Future work is planned to include the influence of spectrum fatigue loads and extended exposure.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Predictive method employed

The predictive method proposed is based on the measured strength distributions obtained from single polyaramid composite pultruded rods tested at different lengths, before and after water immersion. These strength distributions have been characterised by a Weibull two parameter probability model to allow scaling for increases in length (laboratory samples are nominally 100mm, but real tendons are nominally 1000m) according to weakest-link theory. The Weibull model is then modified to allow the prediction of the failure probabilities of parallel bundles of rod as a complete assembly rather than single rod (to simulate a realistic bundle-of-rods type structure). This general method allows the calculation of failure probabilities under a static load for a moisture conditioned bundle of polyaramid pultruded rods of realistic, untestable size and length.

Distribution of single rod strength

Many workers have found the Weibull distribution useful as a model to characterise the variability in observed strengths found in high strength engineering materials such as ceramics and well aligned fibre composites (4). The Weibull distribution is an ideal function for the description of strength as it embodies the physical notions of a) only

allowing positive strength values, and b) that it vanishes at a given minimum positive value (unlike the Gaussian distribution). A typical expression of the Weibull distribution is shown as equation 1,

$$Pf = 1 - \text{EXP} -k\{s/s_0\}^W \dots\dots\dots 1$$

where 'Pf' is the probability of failure under an applied stress of 's', 'k' is a scale factor for the number of contiguous 'units' under this stress, 's₀' is the Weibull scale factor and 'W' the Weibull modulus. The Weibull modulus is a measure of the variability, low values being highly variable.

In this form, the Weibull model can be used to scale between stressed volumes of different size (different numbers of 'units', i.e. values of 'k'), as long as failure of the assembly is the same as failure of any individual 'unit'. This notion clearly applies for the classical chain-of-links case, where failure of a link is the same as failure of the chain. The analysis must be modified for the case of a bundle of chains where failure of a link does not necessarily cause failure of the bundle, as the surviving chains in the bundle may be able to carry the additional load.

Distribution of bundle strengths

For assemblies of stressed 'units' in parallel (but unbonded) the analysis of Coleman (5) may be used to transform the distribution measured for assemblies of 'units' in series, to that of several series of 'units' as a bundle. This gives a method for scaling between the strength distributions measured in single rods to that expected from more realistic (in the case of composite rods or tendons) bundles of rods. In this case, it may be shown that for large bundles, the ratio of mean bundle strength to mean rod strength would be given by equation 2,

$$\text{Strength ratio} = \{W^{(-1/W)} \text{EXP} (-1/W) \Gamma (1+(1/W))\}^{-1} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

where Γ is the gamma function. Note that at any finite variability in rod strength, the bundle of unbound rods will be weaker.

Moisture effects

The effect of absorbed moisture on the tensile strength of the polyaramid fibre is only mild, circa 4% loss after full immersion (2), however the influence of absorbed water on the long term strength of submerged composite tendons should be included in any predictive analysis. The effect of moisture on the resin is to lower the modulus by partial

plasticisation and hence increase the load transfer length which will reduce composite strength. The effect on the composite will also include a degradation of the fibre/resin interface with the same result. However, the full mechanism of moisture induced tensile strength loss in polyaramid composites is not known, but it has generally been observed that moisture uptake is reversible with excellent recovery to dry weight and strength. This lends support to the notion that the process is physical in character, allowing time-temperature-moisture equivalence principles to be employed with some success (6). Hence, the strength distributions measured at one time/temperature/moisture level could be used to calculate the expected distributions at other values by calculation of the appropriate shift factors.

In summary, the model proposed attempts to account for the influence of inherent strength variability, stressed length, bundle size, and absorbed moisture when translating short, dry single rod tensile test data easily obtainable in the laboratory, to the expected probabilities of failure of large tendons in service where strength testing is not possible.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

Strength distribution measurement

High modulus polyaramid/vinyl ester unidirectional pultruded rod has been used throughout. This material was produced commercially as a single batch of fibre-optic guide cable to the required stringent standards, and is expected to represent the uniformity and quality expected from industrial grade material. The nominal rod fibre volume fraction was 72% at a nominal diameter of 2.5mm.

A novel end fitting arrangement was devised that was able to transfer sufficient load (ca 10 kN) into the small diameter rods without rod damage. Aluminium end tubes were bonded to cut rod lengths, the resin from the rod ends being previously removed by a six hour soak in methylene-trichloride. The end tubes comprised an internal taper and socket-spike bonded with an epoxy adhesive; as shown in Figure 1. A universal static test machine was used with modified grips to measure the load to failure at an extension rate of 5mm/min. The failure loads were converted to failure strengths using the measured gross cross-sectional area for each rod.

Strength tests have been conducted at three gauge lengths, 30mm, 100mm, 300mm, and in three conditions of exposure, dry/20°C/65% RH, after 50 days pure water immersion at 20°C, after 50 days pure water immersion at 50°C (tested at 20°C). The immersion time period was sufficient to achieve constant mass at both temperatures.

Weibull data analysis

Figure 2 shows the strength data plotted on Weibull axes for the dry material, and Figure 3 for the 20°C water immersion. The data from the higher temperature exposure has not significantly different from the 20°C data and so is only included in the data summary; Table 1. The linearity of these plots indicates the degree of applicability of the Weibull model. A linear regression analysis has been applied to the data from these figures to obtain values for the Weibull exponents 'W' and for 's_o'. The Weibull constants are shown in Table 1, together with the mean strengths, the coefficients of variation, Weibull scale factors and the calculated strength for a failure probability of 0.1%. Figure 4 plots the strength versus length for the same data, with the strength values used being those that correspond to a failure probability of 0.1%.

Application of the model

Figure 4 illustrates the insensitivity of simple tensile strength to water immersion, and even accelerated immersion (50°C data). The data indicates that the reduction of strength due to the inherent variability and to differences in stressed volume is far more significant than the moisture effect. For this reason, a line has been regressed through all the data in Figure 4, treating the three exposure conditions as a single data set. The equation of the line can be used to scale for changes in length; e.g. at a probability of failure of 0.1%, or better the applied stress on a single 10m rod must be kept below 0.42 GPa, and for a 1000m single rod the stress must be below 0.33 GPa. This value contrasts markedly with the mean strength of 2.0 GPa, determined from tests conducted at 30mm gauge length.

The average Weibull modulus (again pooling the data) is 6.1. This value can be used in equation 2 to calculate the bundle efficiency, or the ratio of rod strength to bundle strength. Using $W = 6.1$ the ratio is nominally 60%. It should be noted that this ratio can be applied to bundles of all sizes. Using the same example as that above, a 1000m bundle of 100 rods would now have a strength of 0.20 GPa for the same probability of failure.

4. DISCUSSION

The Weibull distribution gives a reasonable fit to the basic distribution data, though the fit is better for the material tested dry than for the moisture conditioned material. There is an indication in the wet data that at low stresses some minimum strength is being approached (the down turn in the lower distribution tail in the graphs of Figure 3). A much larger data set would be required to obtain accurate information in this region,

though the error caused by the observed divergence from ideal Weibull behaviour will give conservative strength predictions, allowing the assumption to be maintained with safety.

The validity of weak-link scaling is shown by the linearity of the combined data in Figure 4. A major assumption is that this behaviour remains constant at long lengths. Although valuable additional data could be obtained upto about the 1m point, it is the main aim of this work to predict the strengths of very long lengths where actual testing is not possible for reasons of physical size or cost.

The combined effect of defining a minimum required failure probability, the effect of strength variability, the effect of stressed volume and the effect of moisture (although minimal) is shown clearly by the following example. The mean failure load for rods tested at 30mm is 9.8 kN. If this value was used to calculate a working load of a large bundle, of say 100 rods, by using the number of rods in the bundle as a simple multiplicative factor, then a value of 980 kN would be given. In contrast, the preceding statistical analysis shows that the load should be kept below a value of 102 kN for a failure probability of 1 in 1000.

Several methods could be used to improve the strength translation from short rods to long bundle structures. Firstly, a high priority must be placed on material uniformity with respect to the qualities that control strength. This would be an advantage even if mean strength were sacrificed to achieve low strength variability. Secondly, individual rods could be bound together as a 'macro-composite'; however, flexibility and handling disadvantages may not allow this. Thirdly, care must be taken not to introduce additional strength variability through local damage or mishandling at all stages of manufacture, installation and use.

Additional strength related factors that should be considered in further work include the effect of fatigue loadings, the effect of local bending or kinking (which is very moisture sensitive), internal abrasion, and extended exposure.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. Single point measures of strength can give overly optimistic estimates of the expected strength of large composite structures due to high levels of strength variability. For maximum structural efficiency it may be desirable to sacrifice material strength levels for material strength uniformity when designing large structure.
2. Simple statistical methods are available that can be used to give an extrapolated indication of the expected strength behaviour of large composite structures in the field. When reasonable failure probabilities are required (i.e. $< 0.1\%$) then the maximum

permitted loadings can be surprisingly low.

3. Due to the large inherent variability associated with the composite rods, the potential weight savings in full size structures are not as great as a simple comparison (e.g. with steel) of mean specific strengths would suggest.

4. The equilibrium moisture content did not cause a significant loss of tensile strength in the composite polyaramid tendons tested.

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Figure 2 Distributions of strength for dry rods at the lengths indicated

Figure 3 Distributions of strength for wet rods at the lengths indicated

	TESTED LENGTH (mm)	MEAN FAILURE STRESS (GPa)	CV (%)	W	S ₀ (GPa)	S _{0.001} (GPa)
DRY RODS	30	2.00	12.1	6.3	2.36	0.74
	100	1.78	10.1	6.7	2.08	0.67
	300	1.52	10.7	6.5	1.86	0.55
WET RODS 20°C / 50 days	30	1.87	13.9	5.1	2.27	0.69
	100	1.69	16.5	7.0	1.99	0.65
	300	1.59	16.1	6.2	1.92	0.58
WET RODS 50°C / 50 days	30	1.89	12.6	5.7	2.29	0.70
	100	1.72	11.8	6.1	2.08	0.64
	300	1.57	13.2	5.6	1.88	0.59

Table 1 Tensile test data from single rods

Figure 1 End fitting used for tensile testing pultruded rods

Figure 4 Weibull plot showing the sensitivity of strength to length

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